

**Interreg
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Co-funded by
the European Union

RePo-SUDOE

**High-performance cloud computing service for
screening, identifying, refining and validating
therapeutic targets and drugs for molecular docking
experiments**

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Summary

This report documents the procedure followed to complete Task 1.5 of the RePo-SUDOE project (“Definition of therapeutic targets and drugs of special interest for drug repurposing”), which required the procurement of high-performance cloud computing services for screening, identifying, refining and validating therapeutic targets and drugs for molecular docking experiments. The document is structured as follows:

- Section 1 presents a State of the Art review of drug repurposing, covering available databases, molecular targets, platforms and computational tools.
- Section 2 describes the workflow used to obtain a curated list of drugs and molecular targets of interest, including the selection of proteins with three-dimensional structures available in the Protein Data Bank.
- Section 3 discusses the challenges encountered during protein preparation for molecular docking, including quality filtering, structure cleaning and the use of AlphaFold for structure prediction.
- Section 4 provides representative examples of results obtained using the cloud computing service.
- Section 5 details the computational and storage requirements, justifying the associated expenditure.

The choice of cloud computing infrastructure is justified by the highly specialised and resource-intensive nature of the tasks: large-scale molecular docking across up to 10,000,000 protein-ligand combinations, requiring between 69 and 347 processing days and the handling of over 130 million intermediate and output files. These demands exceed the ordinary technical resources available at the institution, making the associated procurement applicable in accordance with articles 118 and 131 of the Public Sector Contracts Law.

Consortium Partners

This project brings together, for the first time, partners from different SUDOE regions and various stages of the drug development value chain:

- Instituto Politécnico de Guarda
- Universidade da Coruña
- Universidade de Santiago de Compostela

- MD.USE Innovations SL
- Sociedade Portuguesa de Saúde Pública
- Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique
- Asociación Clúster Saúde de Galicia

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Summary and relevance of the report

According to the project schedule, Task 1.5 (“Definition of therapeutic targets and drugs of special interest for drug repurposing”) requires the procurement of high-performance cloud computing services for screening, identifying, refining and validating therapeutic targets and drugs for molecular docking experiments. A search of the State of the Art on the key factors involved in drug repurposing is necessary to achieve this. The ideal starting point for this study is an overview of the drugs available for repurposing (using the literature and publicly available databases), avenues to obtain possible targets (articles, databases, etc.), initiatives, platforms and tools and software involved in drug repurposing. This starting point, which is based on existing knowledge, will be discussed in section 1 of this document.

In section 2, we will discuss the workflow used to obtain a curated and annotated series of drugs, and provide a list of molecular targets and receptors of interest. Molecular targets are usually a protein, DNA, RNA or an enzyme which is studied because it is involved in a biological process. Molecular docking aims to predict how a smaller molecule (such as a drug or chemical compound, and known as a ligand) binds to this target. A common approach in molecular docking studies in cancer research is to begin by identifying genes associated with a disease, by means of data related to gene expression, frequent mutations or other genomic analyses. The encoded proteins are identified based on these genes, as these proteins are usually the therapeutic targets. Proteins with a three-dimensional structure available in structural databases such as the Protein Data Bank are then selected, as this information is essential for performing simulations of molecular docking. The ultimate objective is to predict how different compounds interact with these proteins, which may help identify potential therapeutic agents.

As can be seen in section 3, various obstacles may present themselves during the process involved in preparing proteins for molecular docking studies. In some cases, although the target three-dimensional structure is available, it does not meet minimum quality thresholds to ensure correct molecular docking, even when filtering or correction tools are applied. In a large percentage of cases, the structures must undergo a thorough review and cleaning process in order to remove unwanted molecules, correct errors or complete missing regions. Another situation that frequently arises is the absence of an experimentally resolved structure (which prevents it from being used directly). In these cases, one possible alternative is to predict the structure using tools such as AlphaFold, which provide high quality results, although they also require considerable levels of computational capacity. In overall terms, this stage of the workflow presents a major challenge, both because of the need to incorporate and analyse large amounts of structural and genomic data, and because of the technical resources needed to create reliable models in order to perform accurate molecular docking simulations.

Finally, by way of an example, we present the solution obtained for the experiments performed while using the cloud computing service.

The objective of this report is to set out the procedure followed to complete task 1.5, list the results obtained, and justify the need for the associated expenditure on the cloud computing service.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Introduction to the State of the Art of Medicines

Medicines have been instrumental in the treatment of various diseases, improving people’s quality of life and increasing their life expectancy all over the world. The development of a new drug is a long and costly process, which can take more than a decade and require investments exceeding a billion dollars (DiMasi, Grabowski, and Hansen 2016). This process culminates in rigorous clinical testing to ensure the drug’s efficacy and safety. Technological breakthroughs in recent years have led to the identification and development of more specific and effective drugs, but the pace of drug discovery from scratch remains very slow.

Meanwhile, our growing understanding of molecular biology and genetics has led to the design of targeted therapies, but the costs and time associated with these developments still remain prohibitive. Diseases such as cancer continue to be the focus of intensive research due to their complex nature, which is driving the desire to find more effective therapies (Stratton, Campbell, and Futreal 2009) (Aggarwal 2010).

Against this backdrop, drug repurposing, i.e., identifying new medical uses for existing drugs, has emerged as a promising strategy for accelerating access to effective treatments.

1.2 The Importance of Drug Repurposing

Thanks to drug repurposing, drug development timelines have been reduced from a conventional 10- to 16-year period to a more feasible 3- to 12-year period, enabling researchers to by-pass early-stage safety testing and accelerate the transition to clinical efficacy studies (Parvathaneni et al. 2019). With extensive preclinical and clinical data available, repurposed drugs benefit from prior knowledge of their pharmacokinetics and mechanisms of action, which ensures that potential safety concerns have been thoroughly addressed in previous indications (Cha et al. 2018).

In oncology, a field in which treatment alternatives are urgently needed and often limited due to new agents’ high levels of toxicity, repurposing not only offers a way to rapidly address patients’ needs, but also helps overcome the resistance that is frequently associated with newly synthesized compounds (Orecchioni et al. 2019).

Apart from optimizing development times, drug repurposing creates a window of opportunity for innovative solutions to persistent medical challenges, by involving interdisciplinary collaborations and advanced analytical methodologies (Mishra, Vasanthan, and Malliappan 2024). These methodologies are fertile ground for interdisciplinary partnerships between pharmaceutical companies, academic institutions and non-profit organizations, which can pool their resources and expertise in order to overcome scientific and regulatory obstacles (Polamreddy and Gattu 2019).

1.3 European Drug Repurposing Initiatives

REMEDi4ALL and RePo4EU are initiatives funded by the European Union, aimed at accelerating drug repurposing through multidisciplinary collaboration and advanced digital tools.

[REMEDi4ALL](#) is an initiative led by EATRIS, the European infrastructure for translational medicine. Its consortium consists of 24 organizations, including academic institutions, clinical research bodies, representatives of industry, regulatory experts and patient advocacy groups. The disciplines involved include oncology, molecular biology, biomarker research, clinical oncology, immunotherapy, translational oncology, regulatory science and health policy, among other areas (Jonker et al. 2024). As regards outcomes and inputs, REMEDi4ALL is developing a portfolio of services for drug repurposing and organizing multi-stakeholder expert meetings in order to address challenges of a regulatory, financial and operational nature. These meetings and educational content are part of its broader strategy to facilitate patient-centred research and overcome systemic bottlenecks in drug repurposing (Hewitt et al. 2025).

Meanwhile, RePo4EU [RePo4EU](#) is an initiative which focuses on establishing a unified platform for mechanism-based drug repurposing, with a strong emphasis on digitization and artificial intelligence.

Although it does not specify the precise number of organizations involved, it describes itself as a multi-stakeholder initiative that brings together diverse expertise from academia, industry, healthcare providers and other important sectors. The disciplines represented in this consortium include bioinformatics, clinical research, regulatory science, business development and health technology assessment (HTA) (Ivanov, Getova-Kolarova, and Getov 2024). RePo4EU focuses on creating and deploying a robust digital infrastructure that contains various resource domains, including publication portals, members’ databases, community networks, repositories of cell and animal models, biobanks, and processes ranging from preclinical studies to early clinical phases. The initiative has launched two open access journals and a publishing portal known as Drug Repurposing Central (Dawson 2024).

1.4 Drug Repurposing Databases and Platforms

The literature on drug repurposing first emphasizes the importance of numerous specialist databases containing various types of information. For example, several drug databases contain detailed records of approved and experimental drugs, covering aspects including their chemical composition, therapeutic indications, side effects and molecular targets. Examples include DrugBank, which provides comprehensive information about drugs, including metabolism, targets and pharmacological data, and the Therapeutic Target Database, which focuses on drug-drug interactions and their targets, as well as data from clinical trials (Jin and Wong 2014). These are complemented by chemical compound databases including PubChem, ChemSpider and ChEMBL, which provide data on chemical structures and bioactivity, enabling searches related to similarity and chemical analysis (Tanoli et al. 2021).

Other databases focus on the genetic and protein data essential for identifying targets. For example, gene- and protein-focused resources such as UniProt, BioGrid, Gene Ontology and DisGeNET contain extensive data on gene functions, protein interactions and their associations with diseases. Likewise, specialist databases on 3D structures, such as the RCSB Protein Data Bank (PDB), the AlphaFold database, OCA and Proteopedia, provide access to 3D structures of target proteins, which are crucial for structure-based drug design and molecular docking studies (Tanoli et al. 2021).

In addition to individual databases, there is a growing number of integrated platforms that compile data from this wide range of sources. One of the most prominent examples is the Library of Integrated Network-based Cellular Signatures (LINCS), which includes transcriptomic profiles induced by chemical and genetic perturbations in multiple cell lines. By integrating gene expression, chemical properties and phenotypic responses, LINCS enables signature-based analyses to identify drugs that can potentially be repurposed. Likewise, platforms such as the Drug Repurposing Hub (DRHUB) consolidate information relating to chemical libraries, disease genomics and protein targets into a single interface which enables large-scale computational screening and hypothesis generation (Mohammadi et al. 2020).

In short, current drug repurposing research includes a robust ecosystem of databases, encompassing drug, chemical, gene, protein, structure, and pathway repositories, as well as a growing number of integrated platforms that unify these diverse datasets.

1.5 Bioinformatics Tools for Drug Repurposing

Molecular docking is a computational technique used to predict the preferred orientation of a ligand when it binds to a receptor, usually a protein, in order to identify the orientation with the lowest level of free energy and the most favourable binding interactions. It is primarily based on physical principles including Van der Waals forces, hydrogen bonds and electrostatics, and uses scoring functions to convert energy estimates into docking assessment scores. The advantages of molecular docking include its ability to examine large libraries of compounds and provide detailed structural insights which are invaluable during virtual screening processes. Meanwhile, its disadvantages include limitations such as its inability to fully capture the receptor’s flexibility, and a reliance on scoring functions that may not weight all the components of the binding affinity perfectly. The most widely used software tools in this field include AutoDock, AutoDock Vina, AutoDock FR, DOCK, GOLD, Glide, FlexX and SwissDock, with each offering various trade-offs between computational efficiency and accuracy (Chen, Seukep, and Guo 2020).

Meanwhile, molecular dynamics simulation is a computational method designed to analyse the evolution over time and conformational flexibility of molecular systems at the atomic level, using force field parameters to simulate interactions, including electrostatics, Van der Waals forces and chemical bonds. It provides a dynamic perspective which complements the static snapshots obtained from molecular docking, by providing information on the stability of protein-ligand complexes, predicting transient binding pockets and calculating binding free energies over time. Although it enables thorough evaluation of dynamic molecular interactions, its disadvantages include higher computational costs and challenges related to the accurate sampling of the conformational space, especially in large or highly flexible systems. Popular software platforms used in molecular dynamics include GROMACS, NAMD, CHARMM and AMBER, which are extensively used in academic and industrial settings for drug design and repurposing studies (Azad et al. 2023).

Graph networks are another powerful framework for drug repurposing. They present biological systems in the form of graphs, in which the nodes can represent drugs, proteins, diseases or other biological entities, and the edges denote the interactions or relationships between them. These models may include various types of networks, enabling researchers to incorporate a wide range of data, including protein-protein interactions, drug-target interactions and gene regulatory networks. Graph-based approaches enable new opportunities for drug repurposing to be identified by revealing concealed associations and systemic effects by topological measurement and graph embedding techniques. However, the complexity of biological systems and the dynamic nature of the interactions raise challenges in terms of data integration and the accurate simulation of context-specific biological states (Badkas, De Landtsheer, and Sauter 2021).

Artificial intelligence (AI), including machine learning models and deep neural networks, is increasingly being used to find new uses for existing drugs by leveraging large and heterogeneous biomedical datasets. These AI-based methods can predict drug-target and drug-disease associations by integrating various inputs including chemical structure, multiomics data and clinical outcomes. Machine learning techniques such as support vector machines, random forests and convolutional neural networks have been applied successfully in structure-based drug repurposing processes in order to improve prediction accuracy and optimize the selection of candidates. The use of AI also accelerates hypothesis generation and shortens drug development times, although some challenges related to data standardization and the need for large, well-annotated datasets persist (Choudhury, Murugan, and Priyakumar 2022). This group includes AlphaFold, which is a revolutionary tool driven by advanced AI algorithms that perform atomic-level predictions of protein folding and structure (Desai et al. 2024).

2 Material and methods

2.1 Analysis methodology

The project is focused on locating genes that are involved with any type of cancer. To that end, it uses various resources including IntoGen (Gundem et al. 2010) and Signifinder (Pirrota et al. 2023) to obtain information about genes and transcriptomic signatures associated with cancer. It also contains information on the genes involved in the structure of the YAP/TAZ-TEAD complex (Pobbati and Rubin 2020), a protein complex involved in the regulation of cell proliferation and apoptosis, which are processes that are altered in cancer. This information is used to create a list of genes that are involved in cancer, and which can be used as therapeutic targets.

Based on this list, all the usable information on these genes is sought using Biomart (Drost and Paszkowski 2017) and Ensembl (Dyer et al. 2025), in addition to the gene/protein databases mentioned in the previous section. All the available information is then used to create a database containing the different gene identifiers, general descriptions, functional descriptions, the mechanisms of action which they are involved in, pathways, amino acid sequences, peptide identifiers, any available three-dimensional structures (in PDB or AlphaFold), the drugs they are related to, and the type of cancer they are associated with.

A search for information on FDA- and EMA-approved drugs, and information on drugs that are in the research stage, is also performed. A proprietary database annotated from previous studies, the Anticancer Fund database (<https://www.anticancerfund.org/en>) and DrugBank are used for this. This information is the basis for a list of FDA- and EMA-approved drugs which can be used as therapeutic targets. A database

based on all the available information is also generated. This stores the information about the drugs, their pharmacodynamics, identifiers, mechanisms of action, molecular properties, association with diseases and whether they interact with any gene or protein.

In both cases, if the three-dimensional structure of the protein or drug is not available, AlphaFold and RDKit attempt to generate it.

Finally, a molecular docking analysis is performed using a Docker image (Docker, Inc. 2025) developed by the research team specifically for this project. This image encapsulates various essential tools including AutoDock Vina, Meekeo and MolProbit, providing an integrated and reproducible environment for predicting the interaction between drugs and target proteins.

2.2 Selection of cancer-related genes

2.2.1 Database - IntoGen

IntoGen is a bioinformatics database for identifying cancer driver genes, i.e., those with a genetic alteration which drives tumour development. By analysing large cohorts of tumour sequencing data, IntoGen can detect and prioritize functionally relevant genes in various types of cancer, incorporating genomic and bioinformatics evidence to distinguish between driver mutations and passenger mutations. Although it does not provide protein structures directly, its value as a starting point for molecular docking studies lies in its identification of key genes with information that can be used in other databases such as UniProt or PDB in order to obtain the sequences and structures of the encoded proteins, thereby enabling the exploration of ligand-protein interactions with therapeutic potential.

2.2.2 R Package - Signifinder

Signifinder is an R package designed to allow users to analyse and interpret transcriptomic signatures associated with cancer, and evaluate the activation of key biological processes including proliferation, inflammation, immune response and apoptotic evasion. The package contains a curated collection of gene signatures which have been validated in oncology studies, and permits calculation of activation scores per sample or per group based on gene expression data (e.g. RNA-seq). Although Signifinder does not work with protein structures directly, its usefulness for molecular docking studies lies in its ability to prioritize pathways and active genes in a particular tumour type, which can provide guidance in the selection of relevant target proteins for structural modelling and rational drug design.

2.2.3 The YAP/TAZ-TEAD complex

The YAP/TAZ-TEAD complex is a key functional unit in the Hippo signalling pathway, which is involved in regulating cell growth, proliferation and apoptosis evasion (processes closely associated with the development and progression of cancer). YAP (Yes-associated protein) and TAZ (WWTR1) are transcriptional coactivators which because they do not have their own DNA binding domain, act by interacting with transcription factors in the TEAD family (TEAD1-4). This complex regulates the expression of pro-oncogenic genes when it is active in the nucleus (Pobbati and Rubin 2020).

From the perspective of molecular docking, the YAP/TAZ-TEAD complex is a very important but challenging target. The protein-protein interactions that stabilize this complex (especially at the YAP-TEAD interface) have been the subject of structural studies, and crystal structures for modelling their interaction are now available in PDB. While tools like Signifinder and IntoGen can be used to identify the YAP1, WWTR1, and TEAD1-4 genes as relevant, their protein products are the basis for the rational design of inhibitors or disruptors of their interaction through molecular docking.

The use of this complex as a target is being explored as an emerging therapeutic strategy, particularly in solid tumours with Hippo pathway dysregulation. In this context, molecular docking enables a search for compounds that interfere with YAP/TAZ-TEAD binding or alter the stability of the complex, in order to block the transcriptional activation of oncogenic genes dependent on this axis. Experiments are currently attempting to target 3 zones on the surface of the complex or the central pocket. (Pobbati and Rubin 2020).

2.3 A selection of drugs with known anticancer action

2.3.1 Database - Anticancer Fund

Anticancer Fund is a non-profit organization dedicated to the research and development of cancer treatments. Its database includes information about anticancer drugs, including those that have been approved by the FDA and EMA, as well as compounds subject to ongoing research.

2.3.2 Database - available from research group

A database containing information on anticancer drugs based on previous experiments and studies has been created. This database includes information about pharmacodynamics, mechanisms of action, molecular

properties and their association with different types of cancer. The database also includes information on genes that have been proven to be therapeutic targets for these drugs. This information has been added to the Anticancer Fund database.

2.3.3 Database - Drugbank

DrugBank is a comprehensive database that provides detailed information on drugs and their biological targets. It includes data about the drugs' chemical structure, physicochemical properties, mechanisms of action, interactions and side effects. DrugBank is a valuable tool for pharmacology and biomedicine researchers, enabling the discovery of new uses for existing drugs and the identification of potential therapeutic targets. The database also includes information on the regulatory approval of drugs by agencies such as the FDA and EMA, enabling researchers to swiftly assess a compound's clinical feasibility.

2.4 Bioinformatics Methods

2.4.1 AI-based prediction model - AlphaFold

As mentioned above, AlphaFold is an artificial intelligence system that provides very accurate predictions of the three-dimensional structure of proteins based on their amino acid sequence. This tool has revolutionized structural biology by providing high quality models, even in the absence of experimental structures. AlphaFold generates files in `pdb` format, and these can be used directly in molecular docking studies or in computational simulations. Using AlphaFold to generate the predictions of missing three-dimensional structures has been considered in the cloud computing service.

2.4.2 Computational chemistry library - RDKit

RDKit is a computational chemistry library in Python for handling, analysing and transforming chemical structures. One of its key features is the generation and management of SMILES (Simplified Molecular Input Line Entry System), a text format that represents molecular structures. RDKit uses a database of compounds or by drawing structures to convert them to SMILES, calculate physicochemical properties, generate three-dimensional conformations and prepare ligands in `sdf` format for molecular docking. This tool is essential for automation of the workflow in drug design and virtual screening.

2.4.3 Molecular docking tool - AutoDock Vina

AutoDock Vina is a widely used tool for performing molecular docking, i.e., predicting how a small molecule (such as a drug) binds to a target protein. It uses efficient screening and scoring algorithms that permit examination of multiple ligand conformations and estimations of binding affinity based on energetic parameters. Vina works using protein and compound structural files (both in `pdbqt` format), and is a fast and relatively accurate way of identifying possible binding modes, and prioritizes those that present the most stability. It is an essential tool in the rational design of drugs and in the validation of therapeutic targets.

3 Results obtained using the cloud computing service

3.1 Number of genes in the study

A consolidated list of 3,654 genes was generated from the three main data sources. These genes came from the following sources:

- **Signifinder:** A total of 3,217 genes were identified from 47 cancer-associated transcriptomic signatures.
- **IntoGen:** The database provided 633 genes relevant to the study.
- **YAP/TAZ-TEAD complex:** Seven key genes related to this protein complex were included.

This list includes a comprehensive set of genes with potential therapeutic relevance in the context of cancer.

3.2 Number of protein structures in the study

The following results were obtained from the 3,654 genes identified:

- **28,976** unique peptides in Ensembl.
- **30,229** unique three-dimensional structures available in PDB.
- **14,527** unique three-dimensional structures generated with AlphaFold.
- **5,176** unique Ensembl peptides with no available three-dimensional structures.

3.3 Validation of three-dimensional structures

MolProbity software, a comprehensive and widely used software tool which evaluates the quality of three-dimensional protein structures by analysing detailed geometric and stereochemical parameters, making it essential for assessing structures prior to their use in applications such as molecular docking and molecular dynamics, was used to validate and classify the structures extracted. Its validation approach is based on an all-atom contact analysis, as well as checking main chain and side chain conformations to ensure that the atomic models are physically and chemically plausible.

We considered 4 key metrics for validation:

- The Clashscore: this metric measures the number of serious steric overlaps, i.e. atomic collisions with an inter-atomic distance which is at least 0.4 Å less than the sum of their van der Waals-normalized radii per 1,000 atoms. The lower the Clashscore, the fewer the steric clashes and the more compact the structure. This is critical for identifying models that might otherwise appear acceptable, but which contain local errors that could affect subsequent molecular docking experiments.
- The percentage of residues in the favoured region of the Ramachandran plot (henceforth the Favoured-Ramachandran): this metric evaluates the main chain dihedral angles (ϕ , ψ) of each residue against the empirically derived permitted regions populated by high quality structures. A large percentage of residues in the favoured regions means that the protein main chain adopts energetically favourable conformations which are consistent with known stereochemical constraints, thereby ensuring that the overall folding is reliable for docking experiments.
- The Z-score of the Ramachandran distribution (henceforth the Z-Score): unlike the percentage of favoured residues, the Z-score provides an overall statistical metric for how closely the model's full distribution of dihedral angles resembles that observed in high-quality reference data sets. A Z-score that deviates significantly from zero indicates possible systematic errors in the conformation of the main chain. It is important to identify these deviations, as irregularities in the main chain geometry can lead to errors in the interpretation of molecular interactions during docking experiments.
- The MolProbity score (henceforth the MP-Score): this is a composite metric that combines the Clashscore, Ramachandran statistics and aberrant rotamer percentages into a single quality score. This combined score correlates with the expected resolution of the model, and provides a simple method for comparing the overall quality of different protein structures; models with lower MolProbity scores are deemed to be of higher quality and more appropriate for further computational analysis.

Using MolProbity and these four key metrics ensures that protein models are free of significant steric clashes, have the correct main chain geometry, and accurately represent the physical and chemical properties required for molecular docking studies. This overall validation is crucial not only for the initial assessment of the quality of the structures extracted for docking, but also for filtering and ranking those models in order to select the most reliable candidates for subsequent studies.

Our study prioritized permissiveness, on the grounds that in order for a structure to be considered of sufficient quality, it had to meet the following conditions:

- **Clashscore:** Less than 25
- **Favored-Ramachandran:** 85% or higher
- **Z-Score:** $|Z\text{-score}|$ less than 3
- **MP-Score:** Less than 3

3.3.1 Sample report generated by Molprobity

The quality metrics used to use or rule out a 3D structure were extracted using the MolProbity tool, which performs multiple calculations. All the available structures had to be validated.

A sample report is presented below:

```
===== Molprobity validation =====

Geometry Restraints Library: GeoStd + Monomer Library
Deviations from Ideal Values - rmsd, rmsZ for bonds and angles.
Bond      : 0.022  0.091  1089  Z= 1.059
Angle     : 2.920  12.662  1476  Z= 1.496
Chirality : 0.175  0.532   170
Planarity : 0.025  0.104   180
Dihedral  : 18.333  84.935  521
Min Nonbonded Distance : 2.234

Molprobity Statistics.
All-atom Clashscore : 12.66
Ramachandran Plot:
  Outliers : 2.40 %
  Allowed  : 5.60 %
  Favored  : 92.00 %
Rotamer:
  Outliers : 13.64 %
  Allowed  : 12.73 %
  Favored  : 73.64 %
Cbeta Deviations : 1.75 %
Peptide Plane:
  Cis-proline   : 0.00 %
  Cis-general   : 0.00 %
  Twisted Proline : 0.00 %
  Twisted General : 0.00 %

Rama-Z (Ramachandran plot Z-score):
Interpretation: bad |Rama-Z| > 3; suspicious 2 < |Rama-Z| < 3; good |Rama-Z| < 2.
Scores for whole/helix/sheet/loop are scaled independently;
therefore, the values are not related in a simple manner.
  whole: -2.45 (0.66), residues: 125
  helix: -2.91 (0.92), residues: 14
  sheet: -0.49 (0.80), residues: 42
  loop : -2.14 (0.61), residues: 69

Max deviation from planes:
  Type  MaxDev  MeanDev  LineInFile
ARG    0.038   0.011   ARG A 32
TYR    0.106   0.022   TYR A 14
PHE    0.086   0.009   PHE A 2
TRP    0.189   0.076   TRP A 49
HIS    0.027   0.008   HIS A 98

-----Asn/Gln/His flips-----
```

===== Summary =====

```

Ramachandran outliers = 2.40 %
                    favored = 92.00 %
Rotamer outliers      = 13.64 %
C-beta deviations     = 2
Clashscore            = 12.66
RMS(bonds)           = 0.0219
RMS(angles)          = 2.92
MolProbity score     = 2.96

```

Results written to molprobity.out

Wrote script for Coot: molprobity_coot.py

3.3.2 Overall Validation

A total of 61,958 models/conformations are available from the 30,229 structures retrieved through Biomart and PDB. Each of the models/conformations was treated as an independent structure in this initial validation.

The results of the validation of the three-dimensional structures obtained from the selected genes are presented below.

3.3.2.1 Distribution of the number of downloaded models by structure

- As can be seen in the figure, almost 75% of the structures have a maximum of 10 models.
- Almost all of the remaining 25% of the structures have between 11 and 25 models.
- And less than 3% of the structures have more than 25 models.

3.3.2.2 Clashscore distribution across all models As shown in the figure:

- Slightly more than 65% of the structures have a Clashscore of less than 20.
- 11% of the structures have a Clashscore of between 21 and 30.
- 20% of the structures have a Clashscore of between 21 and 30.

3.3.2.3 Favored-Ramachandran distribution across all models As shown in the figure:

- About 60% of the structures have a Favored-Ramachandran percentage of between 90-100%.
- 14% of the structures have a Favored-Ramachandran percentage of between 85-89%.
- The other structures have a Favored-Ramachandran percentage of less than 85%.

3.3.2.4 Z-Score distribution across all models Based on the Z-Score:

- Almost 50% of the structures have a $|Z\text{-score}|$ of less than 3.
- 10% of the structures have a $|Z\text{-score}|$ of between 3 and 4.
- Finally, the remaining 40% of the structures have a $|Z\text{-score}|$ of over 4.

3.3.2.5 MP-Score distribution across all models The image shows that:

- More than 65% of the structures have an MP-Score of less than 3.
- 25% of the structures have an MP-Score of between 3 and 4.
- Less than 10% of the structures have an MP-Score higher than 4.

3.3.2.6 Feasibility of structures for each metric As can be seen in the table:

- 77% of the structures fulfil Clashscore < 25.
- 71% of the structures fulfil Favored-Ramachandran > 85%.
- 67% of the structures fulfil MP-Score < 3.
- 49% of the structures fulfil |Z-Score| < 3.

The |Z-Score| criterion is therefore the most restrictive when the structures are filtered.

Metrics	Valid	Rejected
Clashscore < 25	47518	14440
Favored-Ramachandran > 85	44320	17638
MP-Score < 3	41812	20146
Z-Score < 3	30315	31643

3.3.2.7 Feasibility of structures according to the number of criteria met According to the table:

- 45% of the structures fulfil all the metrics.

- 62% of the structures fulfil at least 3 metrics.
- 73% of the structures fulfil at least 2 metrics.

Metrics	Valid	Rejected
4 metrics	27934	34024
3 metrics	38255	23703
2 metrics	45367	16591

3.3.3 Filtered Validation

A second validation was carried out, taking only one model per structure into account. To that end, the model with the lowest clashscore, the lowest mp score, the lowest |Rama Z-Score| and the highest percentage of residues in the favoured region of the Ramachandran plot was selected. The total number of models fell from 61,958 to 30,229.

3.3.3.1 Distribution of the number of downloaded models by structure This indicates that one model per structure is to be considered, as shown in the figure below.

3.3.3.2 Clashscore distribution across all models For the filtered Clashscore:

- 85% of the structures have a Clashscore of less than 20.
- 5% of the structures have a Clashscore of between 21 and 30.
- Less than 5% of the structures have a Clashscore higher than 30.

3.3.3.3 Favored-Ramachandran distribution across all models As regards the Favored-Ramachandran:

- More than 85% of the structures have a Favored-Ramachandran percentage between 90% and 100%.
- Slightly more than 5% of the structures have a Favored-Ramachandran percentage of between 85-89%.
- The other structures have a Favored-Ramachandran percentage lower than 85%.

3.3.3.4 Z-Score distribution across all models Looking at the $|Z\text{-Score}|$:

- More than 80% of the structures have a Z-score of less than 3.
- About 10% of the structures have a $|Z\text{-score}|$ higher than 4.
- The other structures have a $|Z\text{-score}|$ of between 3 and 4.

3.3.3.5 MP-Score distribution across all models Looking at the MP-Score:

- About 90% of the structures have an MP-Score of less than 3.
- Slightly more than 5% of the structures have an MP-Score of between 3 and 4.
- Slightly more than 1% of the structures have an MP-Score higher than 4.

3.3.3.6 Feasibility of structures for each metric After filtering and selecting a single model per structure:

- 93% of the structures fulfil Clashscore < 25.
- 94% of the structures fulfil Favored-Ramachandran > 85%.
- 91% of the structures fulfil MP-Score < 3.
- 81% of the structures fulfil |Z-Score| < 3.

This shows that the percentage of structures that meet the criteria increases considerably as a result of being selective when choosing one model per structure.

Metrics	Valid	Rejected
Clashscore < 25	28250	1979
Favored-Ramachandran > 85	28497	1732
MP-Score < 3	27581	2648
Z-score < 3	24536	5693

3.3.3.7 Feasibility of structures according to the number of criteria met As shown in the table, after filtering:

- 79% of the structures fulfil all the metrics.
- 91% of the structures fulfil at least 3 metrics.
- 94% of the structures fulfil at least 2 metrics.

This leaves a considerable increase in the number of structures that meet the quality criteria compared to the overall models.

Metrics	Valid	Rejected
4 metrics	23953	6276
3 metrics	27229	3000
2 metrics	28354	1875

3.4 Identified drugs with anticarcinogenic capacity

A total of 316 anticarcinogenic drugs were identified, of which:

- **292** are FDA/EMA approved. Of these:
 - **164** have three-dimensional structures available in DrugBank.
 - **128** do not have three-dimensional structures available in DrugBank.

3.5 Molecular docking experiments

Various controlled molecular docking experiments were performed to establish the workflow that was developed and the stability of the Docker image created, in terms of its reproducibility and stability in obtaining correct results, regardless of the process followed.

The output data for the process are:

- A log with all the results of the experiment.
- The receptor in `pdbqt` format.
- The ligand in `sdf` format.

3.5.1 Protein structure - Receptor

Each receptor listed in the document is pre-processed with `pdb4amber` and `Meeko`, thereby eliminating unwanted ligands and molecules, correcting atom nomenclature, adding polar hydrogens, eliminating water molecules, calculating partial charges, etc. In short, the optimal three-dimensional structure is calculated in `pdbqt` format. This is the basis for molecular docking experiments. The ternary complex of the human ileal bile acid-binding protein (2mm3), encoded by the `FABP6` gene, is presented as an example.

3.5.2 Drug - Ligand

Each of the ligands listed in the document is pre-processed with `Meeko`, filtering and correcting the input structure, adding polar hydrogens, detecting and defining rotatable bonds, calculating partial charges, etc. In short, the optimal three-dimensional structure is calculated in `pdbqt` format. This is the basis for molecular docking experiments. The three-dimensional structure of abemaciclib is presented as an example. This drug belongs to a class of drugs known as kinase inhibitors.

3.5.3 Results of a molecular docking experiment

After the molecular docking process with Autodock Vina, each experiment provides a numerical result for the bond quality (an example is shown in the document), and an image of the bond can also be obtained. The result of molecular docking between the 2mm3 protein and the abemaciclib ligand is presented as an example. The yellow region represents the surface of the protein.

3.5.4 Output file from an experiment with Autodock Vina

Example of the log output with the result of the experiment on molecular docking between the 2mm3 protein and the abemaciclib ligand. The simulation results, as well as the estimated binding energy and the number of poses generated are shown.

```
#####  
# If you used AutoDock Vina in your work, please cite:      #  
#                                                           #  
# J. Eberhardt, D. Santos-Martins, A. F. Tillack, and S. Forli #  
# AutoDock Vina 1.2.0: New Docking Methods, Expanded Force  #  
# Field, and Python Bindings, J. Chem. Inf. Model. (2021)  #  
# DOI 10.1021/acs.jcim.1c00203                               #  
#                                                           #  
# O. Trott, A. J. Olson,                                     #  
# AutoDock Vina: improving the speed and accuracy of docking #  
# with a new scoring function, efficient optimization and    #  
# multithreading, J. Comp. Chem. (2010)                     #  
# DOI 10.1002/jcc.21334                                     #  
#                                                           #  
# Please see https://github.com/ccsb-scripps/AutoDock-Vina for #  
# more information.                                         #  
#####  
  
Scoring function : vina  
Rigid receptor: /app/2mm3.pdbqt  
Ligand: /app/Abemaciclib.pdbqt  
Grid center: X -31.489 Y 24.374 Z 9.59  
Grid size : X 41 Y 42 Z 35  
Grid space : 0.375  
Exhaustiveness: 10  
CPU: 2  
Verbosity: 2
```

WARNING: Search space volume is greater than 27000 Angstrom³ (See FAQ)

Computing Vina grid ... done.

Performing docking (random seed: 1367858384) ...

0% 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100%

|----|----|----|----|----|----|----|----|----|----|

done.

ENERGY FROM SEARCH: -14.7465

FINAL ENERGY:

Estimated Free Energy of Binding : -10.421 (kcal/mol) [= (1)+(2)+(3)-(4)]

(1) Final Intermolecular Energy : -14.685 (kcal/mol)

Ligand - Receptor : -14.685 (kcal/mol)

Ligand - Flex side chains : 0.000 (kcal/mol)

(2) Final Total Internal Energy : -0.061 (kcal/mol)

Ligand : -0.061 (kcal/mol)

Flex - Receptor : 0.000 (kcal/mol)

Flex - Flex side chains : 0.000 (kcal/mol)

(3) Torsional Free Energy : 4.264 (kcal/mol)

(4) Unbound System's Energy : -0.061 (kcal/mol)

ENERGY FROM SEARCH: -14.721

FINAL ENERGY:

Estimated Free Energy of Binding : -10.403 (kcal/mol) [= (1)+(2)+(3)-(4)]

(1) Final Intermolecular Energy : -14.672 (kcal/mol)

Ligand - Receptor : -14.672 (kcal/mol)

Ligand - Flex side chains : 0.000 (kcal/mol)

(2) Final Total Internal Energy : -0.049 (kcal/mol)

Ligand : -0.049 (kcal/mol)

Flex - Receptor : 0.000 (kcal/mol)

Flex - Flex side chains : 0.000 (kcal/mol)

(3) Torsional Free Energy : 4.257 (kcal/mol)

(4) Unbound System's Energy : -0.061 (kcal/mol)

ENERGY FROM SEARCH: -14.660

FINAL ENERGY:

Estimated Free Energy of Binding : -10.360 (kcal/mol) [= (1)+(2)+(3)-(4)]

(1) Final Intermolecular Energy : -14.221 (kcal/mol)

Ligand - Receptor : -14.221 (kcal/mol)

Ligand - Flex side chains : 0.000 (kcal/mol)

(2) Final Total Internal Energy : -0.439 (kcal/mol)

Ligand : -0.439 (kcal/mol)

Flex - Receptor : 0.000 (kcal/mol)

Flex - Flex side chains : 0.000 (kcal/mol)

(3) Torsional Free Energy : 4.239 (kcal/mol)

(4) Unbound System's Energy : -0.061 (kcal/mol)

ENERGY FROM SEARCH: -14.364

FINAL ENERGY:

Estimated Free Energy of Binding : -10.149 (kcal/mol) [= (1)+(2)+(3)-(4)]

(1) Final Intermolecular Energy : -14.215 (kcal/mol)

Ligand - Receptor : -14.215 (kcal/mol)

Ligand - Flex side chains : 0.000 (kcal/mol)

(2) Final Total Internal Energy : -0.148 (kcal/mol)

Ligand : -0.148 (kcal/mol)

Flex - Receptor : 0.000 (kcal/mol)

Flex - Flex side chains : 0.000 (kcal/mol)

```

(3) Torsional Free Energy      : 4.153 (kcal/mol)
(4) Unbound System's Energy    : -0.061 (kcal/mol)
ENERGY FROM SEARCH: -14.282
FINAL ENERGY:
Estimated Free Energy of Binding : -10.091 (kcal/mol) [= (1)+(2)+(3)-(4)]
(1) Final Intermolecular Energy : -13.678 (kcal/mol)
    Ligand - Receptor           : -13.678 (kcal/mol)
    Ligand - Flex side chains   : 0.000 (kcal/mol)
(2) Final Total Internal Energy : -0.604 (kcal/mol)
    Ligand                      : -0.604 (kcal/mol)
    Flex - Receptor             : 0.000 (kcal/mol)
    Flex - Flex side chains     : 0.000 (kcal/mol)
(3) Torsional Free Energy      : 4.130 (kcal/mol)
(4) Unbound System's Energy    : -0.061 (kcal/mol)
ENERGY FROM SEARCH: -14.025
FINAL ENERGY:
Estimated Free Energy of Binding : -9.909 (kcal/mol) [= (1)+(2)+(3)-(4)]
(1) Final Intermolecular Energy : -13.729 (kcal/mol)
    Ligand - Receptor           : -13.729 (kcal/mol)
    Ligand - Flex side chains   : 0.000 (kcal/mol)
(2) Final Total Internal Energy : -0.297 (kcal/mol)
    Ligand                      : -0.297 (kcal/mol)
    Flex - Receptor             : 0.000 (kcal/mol)
    Flex - Flex side chains     : 0.000 (kcal/mol)
(3) Torsional Free Energy      : 4.055 (kcal/mol)
(4) Unbound System's Energy    : -0.061 (kcal/mol)
ENERGY FROM SEARCH: -13.706
FINAL ENERGY:
Estimated Free Energy of Binding : -9.682 (kcal/mol) [= (1)+(2)+(3)-(4)]
(1) Final Intermolecular Energy : -13.746 (kcal/mol)
    Ligand - Receptor           : -13.746 (kcal/mol)
    Ligand - Flex side chains   : 0.000 (kcal/mol)
(2) Final Total Internal Energy : 0.040 (kcal/mol)
    Ligand                      : 0.040 (kcal/mol)
    Flex - Receptor             : 0.000 (kcal/mol)
    Flex - Flex side chains     : 0.000 (kcal/mol)
(3) Torsional Free Energy      : 3.962 (kcal/mol)
(4) Unbound System's Energy    : -0.061 (kcal/mol)
ENERGY FROM SEARCH: -13.602
FINAL ENERGY:
Estimated Free Energy of Binding : -9.609 (kcal/mol) [= (1)+(2)+(3)-(4)]
(1) Final Intermolecular Energy : -13.148 (kcal/mol)
    Ligand - Receptor           : -13.148 (kcal/mol)
    Ligand - Flex side chains   : 0.000 (kcal/mol)
(2) Final Total Internal Energy : -0.454 (kcal/mol)
    Ligand                      : -0.454 (kcal/mol)
    Flex - Receptor             : 0.000 (kcal/mol)
    Flex - Flex side chains     : 0.000 (kcal/mol)
(3) Torsional Free Energy      : 3.932 (kcal/mol)
(4) Unbound System's Energy    : -0.061 (kcal/mol)
ENERGY FROM SEARCH: -13.515
FINAL ENERGY:
Estimated Free Energy of Binding : -9.547 (kcal/mol) [= (1)+(2)+(3)-(4)]

```

```

(1) Final Intermolecular Energy      : -12.601 (kcal/mol)
    Ligand - Receptor                : -12.601 (kcal/mol)
    Ligand - Flex side chains        : 0.000 (kcal/mol)
(2) Final Total Internal Energy      : -0.914 (kcal/mol)
    Ligand                            : -0.914 (kcal/mol)
    Flex - Receptor                   : 0.000 (kcal/mol)
    Flex - Flex side chains           : 0.000 (kcal/mol)
(3) Torsional Free Energy            : 3.907 (kcal/mol)
(4) Unbound System's Energy         : -0.061 (kcal/mol)

```

mode	affinity (kcal/mol)	dist from best rmsd l.b.	mode rmsd u.b.
1	-10.4207	0.0000	0.0000
2	-10.4028	2.2308	2.9498
3	-10.3597	3.1319	10.1589
4	-10.1492	5.9099	9.9205
5	-10.0914	3.5844	10.2960
6	-9.9089	7.2567	12.1215
7	-9.6821	1.7058	2.2227
8	-9.6088	6.3996	11.1075
9	-9.5470	3.2457	11.3549

4 Storage and computing

A minimum estimate of the computational calculations is presented below, with another estimate of the storage space used in the cloud computing service. The process required a large number of iterations to refine it properly, and as such the actual space occupied and actions taken were greater than the estimates for the process of testing and learning about the cloud computing service. However, a standard estimate of the minimum requirements under usual circumstances is provided as an example.

4.1 Requirements for the management of protein structures

The molecular docking process involves the interaction of proteins and ligands, which are represented by three-dimensional structures stored in `pdb` and `sdf` file formats respectively. As mentioned above, these structures are taken from various databases, including the PDB and the AlphaFold database.

The total number of `pdb` files considered is estimated at approximately 45,000-50,000 files. Since the size of each `pdb` file varies depending on the complexity of the protein structure, this figure requires considerable storage space.

4.2 Requirements for the management of anticarcinogenic drugs

Ligands, which are the small molecules with which proteins interact in the molecular docking process, must also be taken into account. These ligands primarily come from the DrugBank three-dimensional structure database, and from computational libraries such as RDKit.

The total number of `sdf` files is estimated at approximately 200. As with the proteins, each `sdf` file varies in size depending on the complexity of the ligand, which has an impact on the storage capacity required.

4.3 Requirements for molecular docking experiments

Since the molecular docking strategy used is greedy (i.e., an all-against-all analysis), the total combinations are the combination between each of the 50,000 proteins and the 200 ligands, giving a total of: 50,000 *

200 = 10,000,000 combinations. This large number of combinations is crucial for calculating the amount of storage space required for the intermediate files and the output files generated during the simulations.

The molecular docking process involves importing the input files (protein and ligand structures), as well as generating a large number of intermediate files containing the partial results of the process, and finally the output files, which contain the final results of the molecular docking.

It is estimated that 10 to 15 intermediate files were generated for each protein-ligand combination in each molecular docking combination. These files contain essential information about steps in the simulation, energy interactions and other important data.

Three output files are also generated for each combination. These contain the final results and information about the binding of the ligands to the proteins, as well as the quality of the binding.

- $50,000 \times 200 \times 10-15 = 100,000,000 - 150,000,000$ intermediate files.
- $50,000 \times 200 \times 3 = 30,000,000$ output files.
- It is important to note that due to the large amount of data they contain and the fact that they are necessary for the detailed analysis of each simulation, the intermediate files occupy a significant portion of the storage available.

4.4 Computation time

The time required to run a molecular docking simulation depends on various factors, including the size and complexity of the protein and ligand structures, as well as the power of the computational resources available. It is estimated that between 1 and 5 minutes of computation using a 10-core processing configuration are required for each molecular docking.

En base a las 10.000.000 combinaciones de acoplamiento molecular, el tiempo total de cómputo requerido ha sido:

- $50,000 \times 200 \times 1-5 \text{ minutes} = 100,000 - 500,000$ minutes.
- $50,000 \times 200 \times 1-5 \text{ minutes} / 60 = 1,666 - 8,333$ hours.
- $50,000 \times 200 \times 1-5 \text{ minutes} / 60 / 24 = 69 - 347$ days.

This calculation gives us an estimated range of the total computational time for all molecular docking simulations ranging from 69 to 347 days, depending on the complexity of the proteins and ligands involved.

The molecular docking process carried out involved a significant consumption of computational and storage resources, given the large number of combinations between proteins and ligands, as well as the number of intermediate and output files generated during the process. Between 100 million and 150 million intermediate files were handled during the process, in addition to the 30 million output files generated at the end of each simulation.

The expenditure on storage infrastructure was essential for handling the large number of files involved. Likewise, the estimated total computation time of between 69 and 347 processing days was in fact the time needed to complete all the simulations. This time was distributed efficiently across the computing resources available.

The storage and computing infrastructure used was adequate to ensure the project's viability and efficiency, and as such justifies the costs associated with these operations, given that the simulations were performed successfully and within the anticipated deadlines. All the outputs from the tools used are available. This document contains examples obtained from the cloud computing processing of the most important examples, and explains the process carried out and the computational and storage complexity. The summarized list with the "Definition of therapeutic targets and drugs of special interest for drug repurposing" obtained will be sent as a deliverable from the project, thereby fulfilling the primary objective of the report.

5 Docker image generated with the cloud computing service software

We have mentioned the creation and use of a Docker image with the software required for the analysis, which ran on the cloud computing service, throughout this document. This Docker image is available at:

- Code repository on GitHub (<https://github.com/MALL-Machine-Learning-in-Live-Sciences/dock-tools>)
- Downloadable file in Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/records/15064460>)

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